

PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF NP TYPES IN VARIOUS DISCOURSES**Miralimova Madina**

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola ingliz tilidagi so'z yasashining samarasiz turlari, ularning turli kontekstlardagi pragmatik jihatlarini yoritishga bag'ishlanadi. Maqolada ko'plab misollar orqali, samarasiz usullarda yasalgan so'zlarning ma'nolari va kelib chiqishi o'quvchiga tushunarli bo'lishi uchun keng tahlil etilgan. Keltirilgan barcha misollar ishonchli elektron manbaalardan olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: samarasiz so'z yasash usullari, tovush almashish, urg'u almashish, tovushga taqlid qilish, qorishtirish, ortidan hosil qilish.

Abstract: This article is devoted to highlighting ineffective types of word formation in English, their pragmatic aspects in different contexts. In the article, the meanings and origins of words made in ineffective ways are analyzed in order to be understandable to the reader through many examples. All examples are taken from reliable electronic sources.

Key words: non-productive word building means, sound interchange, stress interchange, sound imitation, blending, back formation.

At present, the ways of word building, word origins, language group that they belong to and other similar aspects are of great importance in the formation of a particular language. In general, there are two types of English word formation: productive and nonproductive. In this article, we will focus more on unproductive types of word formation and their various pragmatic aspects in different contexts.

In English word-building system there are some ways of word formation which are stress interchange, sound imitation or onomatopoeia, blending and back formation.

Although more or less they have lost their productivity nowadays, they are still in usage in various contexts.

At the initial stage we can involve sound interchange as a passive word formation type. This is the way of word-building when some sounds are changed to form a new word. Even though it is considered as non-productive in Modern English, it used to be productive in Old English and could be met in other Indo-European languages. Sound interchange can be for different reasons. It can be the result of Ancient Umlaut or vowel mutation which is the result of palatalizing the root vowel because of the front vowel in the syllable coming after the root. In many cases there are two types of them: vowel and consonant interchange, for instance, life – to live, bath – to bathe, breath – to breathe etc.

The following example can be the word bleeding. It gives different pragmatic meanings in diverse contexts, as an adjective: to have a bleeding [cut, wound, sore, laceration]; to have a bleeding disorder; my bleeding heart aches!; to have a bleeding heart for; she is a real bleeding heart/ a bleeding-heart liberal; a Bleeding Heart [flower, plant].

Also some slangs can be mentioned: UK: what a bleeding [mess, idiot]!; UK: don't be a bleeding [fool, idiot]!; UK: don't be so bleeding [cheeky, impatient, nosy]!; UK: he looks so bleeding [bored, angry, upset, lost].

Some idioms are made as well: (it) has bled me [white, dry]; my heart bleeds for you; bleed a patient with leeches.

Besides that, stress interchange were mostly met in verbs and nouns of Romanic origin: nouns have the stress on the first syllable and verbs on the last syllable, e.g. accent - to accent. The explanation of this phenomenon can be in the following way: French verbs and nouns had different structure when they were borrowed into English, verbs had one syllable more than the corresponding nouns. As a consequence of dropping of borrowed sounds we have such pairs in English as: to af`fix -affix, to conflict- conflict, to export -export, to extract - `extract etc.

Correspondingly, sound imitation is the way of word-building when a word is formed by imitating different sounds. There are some semantic groups of words formed by means of sound imitation: to catch the "real" tweeter, Weiner explained that he had hired an Internet security firm to investigate;

Her shoes **clattered** on the stone floor; You might **chatter** with your workmates about the weather or where you'll eat lunch. [<https://www.google.com>]

Blends are words formed from a word-group or two synonyms, briefly, they consist of the combination of abbreviation and composition. In order to form a blend we clip the end of the first component and the beginning of the second component. Therefore, we have a compound- shortened word. One of the preliminary blends in English was the word «smog» from two synonyms: smoke and fog which means smoke mixed with fog. From the initial component the beginning is taken, from the second one the end, «o» is common for both of them. From pragmatic point of view, there are some examples: A **magalog** is a promotional copy of a magazine, usually in a 12-page catalog format. **Magalogs** help introduce magazines to new readers, or function as a catalog formatted as a magazine; -The more aesthetic want no part of slimnastics but want to express themselves in movement provided by Mime and Movement or Modern Dance classes. [<https://www.collinsdictionary.com>] - "My brother and his friend are in such a bromance; they hang out almost everyday!" (brother + romance). [<https://blog.lingoda.com/en>]

Another unproductive type of word formation is back formation, which is opposite to suffixation. In this way a word is formed by dropping the final morpheme to form a new word, that is why it is called back formation. [<https://multiurok.ru/files/lecture-3-productive>]

For example, the word "Beatnik" was suggested by Herb Caen, a San Francisco columnist, similarly to the Russian word "sputnik", which was popular at that time. This term stands for a person associated with, the "BeatGeneration". -He was far, far different than the laughing, beatnik jabbering, youngster he had always

seemed. Black Man's Burden. Another new term, freelance, was suggested for the first time, by the Scottish novelist, Walter Scott. According to his novel Ivanhoe, "Free Lances" were hired as militants for a fee:

-As a **freelance** writer, I depend for my living on easy relations with magazines, creative-writing departments, and so on;

-They will not actually steal, but they will cheat you every time and chortle over it (chuckle + snort);

- She never lost her **enthusiasm** for teaching. The news was greeted with a lack of **enthusiasm** by those at the meeting;

-She then goes on with a similar analysis of the near-synonyms, demonstrating that they in fact collocate with other sets of nouns;

-From the viewpoint of the classification of word combinations relating to **collocations**, these approaches determine, for a given verbal **collocate**, a class of bases. [<https://dictionary.cambridge.org>];

-The notion of **addicts** as passive victims of their **addiction** is a gross simplification;

-He spends much of his free time helping other **addicts** and alcoholics find freedom; -

Gasohol is a mixture of one part ethanol (commonly known as grain alcohol" or beverage alcohol) and nine parts unleaded gasoline. The ethanol can be produced from several types of plant material using technology which is currently available, and in most cases gasohol can be substituted for gasoline with only minor changes in mileage and performance. In conclusion, ways that are considered to be less productive in word formation still have their value. All the examples mentioned above prove that words made by means of sound interchange, stress interchange, blending or back formation give different pragmatic meanings in various discourses. Such as, idiomatic, positive and negative meanings and slangy meaning.

References

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